

Bright nights, dim futures: Artificial light at night disrupts behavioral patterns in animals: A review

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Abstract

The widespread use of artificial light at night has transformed our environment, affecting the daily activities of nearly all animals. The natural separation between day and night has been severely disrupted. The natural behaviors of organisms have been altered due to extended lighting periods resulting from disrupted circadian regulation. This includes changes in the timing and duration of foraging, feeding, resting, waking, migration, and reproduction. Diurnal species, whose reproductive cycles are more predictable in natural environments, have also suffered from this illuminated environment. This review highlights the role of the artificial light environment on various behavioral aspects, and hence the need to protect the natural darkness to maintain the normal behaviors and survival of a wide range of animals.

Keywords: ALAN, Behaviour, Urbanization, Darkness

Introduction

Artificial light refers to any human-made light source designed for comfort and convenience. These include automobile lights, streetlights, electric bulbs or LEDs, lamps, lasers, and electronic devices, among others [1-3]. Besides boosting human activity and improving safety and visibility, extending the light period has also increased productivity in both industrial and agricultural settings. It has allowed various cultural, athletic, and adventurous activities to take place without natural light sources like sunlight. The widespread use of artificial lights aimed to solve various problems and uphold the standards of human civilization [4-6]. While artificial light offers many benefits, recent years have highlighted its disadvantages across multiple species. Artificial light at night (ALAN) has impacted different behavioral aspects, such as activity-rest cycles, sleep-wake patterns, foraging, brain functions, cognition, mood, immune responses, hormone secretion, singing, nest building, reproduction, and migration among different organisms. This review aims to explore how ALAN influences various behaviour patterns in animals, especially reproductive behaviors and physiology in birds.

Activity-rest pattern and sleep-wake cycle

Activity-rest and sleep-wake cycles occur naturally in all animals, including humans. However, ALAN blurs the boundary between day and night, altering these patterns in both diurnal and nocturnal animals. Studies show that ALAN prolongs the light period, reducing night hours. Increased light exposure extends diurnal activity, significantly boosts nocturnal activity, and causes earlier activity onset and delayed activity offset [7,8]. Activity-rest-sleep patterns at night have been disrupted by ALAN, which disturbs the natural separation between day and night, misaligning clock-controlled functions like activity and sleep-wake cycles. This disturbance causes a shift in activity away from the natural schedule. ALAN also

affects sleep-wake cycles across animals, with birds being particularly sensitive. Night exposure to light reduces sleep duration in insects (e.g., honey bees: *Apis mellifera*)[9], causes more early awakenings in birds (e.g., great tits: *Parus major*)[10] Australian pigeons: *Columba livia*, wild magpies: *Cracticustibicentyrannica*, [11] zebra finches: *Taeniopygia guttata*, [8, 12], and increases nocturnal vigilance (e.g., peahens: *Pavo cristatus*) [13]. Sleep is crucial for all animals, linked to behaviors like social bonding, mood, cognition, and memory. Animal studies, especially on birds, show that ALAN delays sleep onset and advances sleep offset, reducing sleep quantity and quality. ALAN decreases nocturnal sleep[12,14,15] and worsens sleep quality by increasing sleep bouts and reducing average bout duration [12,14,15]. It also disturbs daily sleep-wake cycles and rhythms, and alters sleep structure in mammals (e.g., Wistar rats: *Rattus norvegicus*) [16], humans [17]. ALAN disrupts activity-rest patterns, leading to increased nocturnal activity, prolonged wakefulness, and heightened alertness, which all negatively affect total sleep quality and duration [18].

Foraging and feeding

Artificial light influences foraging behavior, alters predator-prey dynamics, and shifts foraging times and food intake, as evident by recent researches. Reduced foraging activity was observed in bats under various night lighting conditions (color and intensity) [19,20]. Another study found that ALAN disrupts the natural nocturnal foraging of kangaroo rats (*Dipodomys stephensi*), which forage less to avoid nocturnal predators like owls [21]. In diurnal birds like zebra finches, an increase in nighttime food activity and disruption of the natural feeding rhythm and frequency were observed under dim night light exposure [8, 15]. Coastal lighting has decreased foraging and feeding activity in mice, possibly due to reduced visibility and increased vulnerability to predators [22]. ALAN shifts the timing, duration, and movements associated with foraging and feeding, which can alert predators to catch its prey, leading to a decline in prey populations and hence affecting prey-predator relationships [23].

Brain functions, cognition, and personality

Brain functions and cognition are also affected by ALAN, which influences brain structure and activity across many species. For example, night light exposure in spiders impacts activity and causes changes in brain size. Even low levels of ALAN (1.5 lux) at night alter the expression of immediate early genes like cFos and ZENK, which are involved in vision, movement, learning, and hormone regulation in birds [24]. ALAN can impair cognitive abilities such as learning and memory, as seen in birds like Indian house crows (*Corvus splendens*) [25], and zebra finches (*Taeniopygia guttata*) [12, 15], and it can provoke depression in Nile grass rats (*Arvicanthis niloticus*)[26].

Hormone secretion and immune responses

Animals living under artificial light suffer from disrupted circadian control, which introduces physiological disturbances and has effects such as weakening immunity and shifting hormone release. For instance, in blackfield crickets (*Teleogryllus commodus*), even 1 lux of light decreases haemocyte levels, a key component of insect immunity [27]. Similar immune effects were observed in wild great tit (*Parus major*) nestlings, with lower levels of haptoglobin and nitric oxide in light-exposed chicks[28]. In rodents, exposure to just 5 lux of night light suppressed cell-mediated immune responses [29]. Reduced melatonin and growth hormone levels in cattle (Holstein, *Bos Taurus*) [30], increased glucocorticoid levels in rats (*Rattus norvegicus*)[31], and hormonal imbalances in Eurasian perch (*Perca fluviatilis*)[32] all point to endocrine disruption caused by artificial light. All these studies confirm that light at night significantly disrupts hormonal and circadian homeostasis in animals.

Migration

Artificial shore light attracts sea turtles to beaches, disrupting their migratory routes after hatching[23,33]. Similar disorientation caused by artificial light affects nocturnal insects,

which are attracted and confused by the lights [34]. For migrating birds, ALAN introduces risks such as disorientation and increased energy expenditure, possibly delaying arrivals at breeding sites and mismatching optimum offspring development conditions (vegetation, temperature, humidity). Additionally, collisions with lit buildings or towers may cause injuries, reducing fitness and reproductive success[35-37].

Breeding behavior

ALAN also affects nest building and reproduction by disrupting hormonal and behavioral cues critical for nesting, breeding, and parental care. Recent research suggests that ALAN can inhibit female pheromone release, reduce male attraction, induce male sterility, and disrupt female egg-laying in insects, impacting breeding success and population sustainability[34]. A study by Yang and Nakamura (2022) noted that light pollution influences spatial distribution, like increasing nesting density of cavity-dwelling ants near light sources, potentially altering ecological functions [38]. Exposure to ALAN in wasps (*Venturia canescens*) led to increased night-time feeding and egg-laying, which is usually uncommon under natural conditions [39]. Many studies on birds have highlighted how urban light pollution affects reproductive timing, nest site selection, survival rates, and ecological interactions. For example, in great tits (*Parus major*), artificial light influences nest size and height, with some birds building thinner nests to limit exposure to light at night [40]. Conversely, others like Pawel Podkowa and Adrian Surmacki(2017) found that great tits prefer brighter nest sites, supporting the idea that ambient light inside nests can improve offspring fitness by assisting with feeding and offspring recognition [41]. Similarly, female European blackbirds (*Turdus merula*) tend to nest in well-lit areas, theorized to enhance nestling survival from nocturnal predators [42]. These findings highlight the role of urban lighting in shaping nest size and site preference, affecting ecological dynamics.

ALAN also influences breeding timing, with studies showing that birds in artificially lit environments tend to breed earlier. For example, blackbirds in lighted areas started reproduction and moulting earlier than those in dark places [42, 43]. Wang et al. (2021) similarly observed that birds select brighter sites for nesting in urban areas to safeguard offspring from nocturnal predators [44]. Dominoni and his colleagues (2020) noted that artificial light combined with warmer spring temperatures advances breeding in great tits, [45] although it may also cause mismatches with food availability. Peter J. Sharp (2025) explained that birds normally use daylight length to time breeding [46], but ALAN can create confusion. Overall, these studies suggest that artificial night lighting disturbs the natural rhythm of breeding behaviors, potentially affecting life cycles and causing ecological impacts in urban landscapes. Overall, ALAN disturbs most physiological processes, including migration, sleep, feeding, hormone release, and brain functions, altering the timing and success of reproduction, which are essential for species survival. Ecologically, it can cause mismatches between breeding periods and food availability.

Conclusion

Artificial light at night is beneficial for modern living and societal progress; however, the same light is also harmful for wildlife. The widespread use of artificial lights at night has deprived animals of receiving natural darkness and as a result, animals suffer from disruption of the natural body clock, affecting their vital clock-controlled functions including daily activity, feeding, sleep, and breeding behaviour. Therefore, it is important to restrict or manage the lighting conditions, used only when needed, with proper shielding and must be wildlife friendly to protect and maintain the natural environments in the interest of both development and animal life.

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Figure 1 shows the sources of natural and artificial light at night in an urbanized area. Light measurement given in lux (lx).

Figure 2. Artificial light at night disrupts the circadian rhythms of animals, leading to misalignment of physiological activities like sleep, foraging, migration, and reproduction.

